

Alliance Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum

Meeting Summary – 20th May 2025

Introduction

The UK Health Data Research Alliance (the Alliance) convened its fifth Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum on 20th May 2025. The meeting was co-chaired by Dr Macey Murray (Senior Research Fellow, MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL) and Associate Professor Fiona Lugg-Widger (Deputy Director of Data, Centre for Trials Research, Cardiff University). Participants included trialists, researchers, data custodians, public representatives, funding organisations, and NHS and academic stakeholders.

Key Themes and Objectives

The meeting covered several important topics, with a particular focus on:

- Updates from NHS England and the BHF Data Science Centre on infrastructure supporting data-enabled trials
- Presentation and discussion of the draft Green Paper on streamlining data access for trials
- Structured breakout discussions on implementation pathways for the Green Paper's three core recommendations:
 - Establishing a national health data research service
 - Developing an objective standard for assessing adequacy of consent to use health data
 - Creating precedent-set pathways for common trial datasets

NHS England and BHF Data Science Centre Updates

Matt Sydes and Laura Hobbs (NHS England) presented on the NHS Data for Research & Development (R&D) programme and the NHS DigiTrials service. Key highlights included:

- The secure data environment (SDE) network continues to expand, providing linked, privacy-enhanced access to health data covering 57 million people across England
- The platform enables federated access across regional SDEs and is underpinned by the Five Safes, FAIR principles, and patient/public involvement
- NHS DigiTrials supports feasibility studies, recruitment, and outcome measurement for trials using linked health data, with capacity to send 150,000 invitations per day and support from behavioural science to optimise enrolment

Ross Forsyth and Sarah Lessels (BHF Data Science Centre) [presented on the UK Clinical Cohorts Trusted Research Environment](#) (UK CLIC TRE). Key highlights included:

- The TRE supports linkage of cardiovascular cohorts to NHS data to improve long-term follow-up and research efficiency

- Built in partnership with SAIL Databank, with an ambition to serve UK-wide needs
- Currently focused on pseudonymised data access, with future plans to support recontact and clinical trial use
- Emphasis on streamlining governance and improving data curation to reduce delays and improve usability for researchers

Draft Green Paper Presentation

Marina Bobou (MRC CTU at UCL) [presented the current draft of the Green Paper](#), developed by the Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum working group. Key points included:

- The paper identifies five key barriers to data access for clinical trials: fragmented approval systems, inconsistent consent standards, limited data custodian capacity, retrospective application of new standards, and insufficient inclusion of patient/participant voices
- It proposes three recommendations to address these issues:
 - Establishing a national health data research service to simplify and unify access processes across the UK
 - Developing an objective national standard for assessing adequacy of consent to use health data, co-produced with patients and aligned with future regulatory change
 - Creating precedent-set review pathways for common datasets to reduce administrative burden and speed up approval timelines
- Each recommendation aims to streamline approval processes and increase consistency for trials accessing health systems data
- The draft incorporates public involvement throughout and seeks to balance legal, ethical, and practical considerations across trial types and data custodians

Breakout Discussions: Implementing Green Paper Recommendations

Participants engaged in breakout discussions focused on three key recommendations and fed back their views regarding the main barriers, incentives and proposed actions to ensure implementation:

1. Develop a nation-wide data access system (Health Data Research Service) that is fit for trials.

Key barriers identified were uncertainty around the new service, the risk of overlooking trialist needs, and the failure to build on existing infrastructure. Participants also highlighted a lack of shared case studies and the challenge of engaging policy makers effectively.

Key incentives identified were the potential to build public trust by referencing the independence of the Sudlow Review, encouraging collaboration across the real-world data (RWD) landscape, and motivating commercial engagement beyond financial return.

Suggested next steps included engaging with Cathie Sudlow, the UK Health Data Research Alliance, and the Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group. Participants also recommended broadening public

involvement (for example, via webinars with the Patients Association) and proactively communicating the Green Paper and its recommendations.

2. Develop an Objective Standard for Consent

Key barriers identified were inconsistencies in how data custodians interpret risk and assess the adequacy of consent, as well as the complexity of aligning legal frameworks across the four nations. Participants also noted a lack of clarity on how the standard would work in practice and ensure buy-in from the public.

Key incentives identified were the importance of clearly articulating the risks of not sharing data, using concrete use cases to support proportionality, and sustaining collective trust through consistent, transparent communication.

Suggested next steps included collaboration between the BHF Data Science Centre and other key stakeholders, to assess existing consent wording and adopt a “no surprises” approach. Participants proposed surveying custodians to identify their key criteria and reviewing current guidance from regulators such as the ICO.

3. Precedent set Pathway for Common Datasets

Key barriers identified were the complexity of working across departmental datasets, delays in timely data access, and the risk of certain datasets becoming overused while others are overlooked. Differences in data fields and collection purposes across UK nations were also noted.

Key incentives identified were a reduction in application volume and admin burden, greater efficiency through standardisation, and improved ability to validate trial outcomes. Participants also saw potential for broader UK-wide collaboration and increased engagement from new users.

Suggested next steps included identifying commonly used datasets to pilot precedent pathways, engaging data providers and charities to address barriers, and developing standardised protocols. It was also agreed that patient and public involvement (PPIE) should be embedded throughout, particularly in the design of the new Health Data Research Service.

Next Steps

- The working group will finalise the Green Paper in June 2025, incorporating workshop feedback
- Further stakeholder input will be sought, including from public contributors, Alliance Council members, and the Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group
- Publication of the Green Paper is expected by July 2025
- A decision on the next Forum topic will be informed by this [participant survey](#).

Appendix

Contributing Organisations
BHF Data Science Centre
Cardiff University
Cystic Fibrosis Trust
Health Data Research UK (HDR UK)
MRC Clinical Trials Unit at University College London (UCL)
Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA)
Understanding Patient Data
NHS England
Optimum Patient Care
Our Future Health
Public Health Scotland
University College London (UCL)
University of Dundee
Welsh Government